

Synthesis and characterization of iron(III), cobalt(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and mercury(II) complexes of 4-piperidinomethyl antipyrine

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Piperidinomethyl antipyrine (PMA) was synthesized using Mannich reaction and its complexes of iron(III), cobalt(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and mercury(II) were prepared and characterized by elemental analysis and UV, IR and ¹H NMR spectral studies. The bidentate chelation of PMA, bonding through carbonyl oxygen of antipyrine moiety and C-N-C of piperidine ring is suggested. Based on the UV spectral and magnetic moment data, octahedral geometry for iron(III) and copper(II) and tetrahedral geometry for cobalt(II), zinc(II) and mercury(II) complexes are assigned. The results of thermal and kinetic studies and antimicrobial activity of the complexes are also reported.

Due to strong basic character¹ of the carbonyl group in antipyrine it is known to form metal complexes which behave as antimicrobial^{2,3}, antirheumatic⁴, antipyretic⁵ and analgesic⁶ drugs. In continuation of our earlier work reported⁷⁻¹⁰ on Mannich base derivatives of antipyrine and their transition metal complexes we are reporting here our extended studies.

Results and discussion

Elemental analysis :

PMA is a yellow coloured waxy solid melting at 72°C.

The results of elemental analysis for the recrystallised product are given in Table 1. Elemental analysis shows the stoichiometry of the complexes as MX₂.PMA for the anhydrous complexes and MX₃.PMA for the hydrated complex.

Electrical conductance data :

Conductance measurement of 10⁻³ M solution for the complexes in DMF registers values in the range of 10-20 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ for Zn^{II}, Hg^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, which indicates the complexes to be non-electrolytes. For Co^{II}

Table 1. Analytical and conductivity data of the ligand and its complexes. Percentages observed (calcd.)

Complex	Elemental analysis				λ _M
	Metal	X ⁻	C	H	
PMA	-	-	71.55 (71.58)	8.05 (8.07)	-
FeCl ₃ .PMA.H ₂ O	12.00 (12.00)	22.88 (22.89)	42.80 (42.82)	4.90 (4.94)	89.0
CoCl ₂ .PMA	14.18 (14.20)	17.08 (17.11)	49.15 (49.16)	5.53 (5.54)	83.1
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .PMA	13.43 (13.44)	26.23 ^a (26.24)	43.15 (43.17)	4.89 (4.86)	20.0
ZnBr ₂ .PMA	12.80 (12.81)	31.32 (31.32)	39.97 (39.99)	4.48 (4.50)	19.5
HgCl ₂ .PMA	36.06 (36.04)	12.73 (12.75)	36.63 (36.65)	4.10 (4.13)	10.0

PMA = 4-Piperidenomethyl antipyrine. ^aObtained from the difference between the mass of the complex and the mass of the other constituents excluding anion. λ_M in Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ for 10⁻³ DMF solution of the complexes.

and Fe^{III} complexes the conductance value is in the range of 80–90 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹. This higher value of conductance may be due to the partial replacement of the coordinated halide by the strong donor solvent molecule.

IR and far-IR spectra :

The bands at 1666 and 1108 cm⁻¹ are due to the carbonyl stretching mode and ν_{C-N-C} stretching vibration of piperidine. Pyrazolone stretching and bending vibrations appear at 1493 and 1449 cm⁻¹ respectively. A new band at 2936 cm⁻¹ is due to the insertion of the piperidine moiety into the ring in PMA.

In the case of iron(III) chloro complex a band observed at 3373 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of OH group. The bending, rocking and wagging modes of water observed at 1626, 870 and 593 cm⁻¹ respectively for the chloro complex suggest the presence of coordinated water. The ν_{C=O} band observed at 1630 cm⁻¹ is indicative of the coordination of carbonyl oxygen to the metal atom. The ν_{C-N-C} of piperidine ring occurring at 1108 cm⁻¹ in the ligand is lowered by 174 cm⁻¹ in the complex indicating the involvement of tertiary nitrogen atom also in coordination. The ν_{C=O} and ν_{C-N-C} bands in the cobalt(II) chloro complex are observed at 1602 and 1048 cm⁻¹ and they show a negative shift by about 64 and 60 cm⁻¹ respectively which points to a bidentate chelate bonding through the carbonyl oxygen and tertiary nitrogen atom of piperidine. IR spectrum of copper(II) nitrate complex shows three strong bands at 1507, 1306 and 1047 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to ν₁, ν₅, ν₂ respectively of the coordinated nitrate group. Since the difference between ν₅ and ν₁ is 201 cm⁻¹, it is inferred¹¹ that the nitrate group is coordinated bidentately in this complex. Negative shifts observed for ν_{C=O} and ν_{C-N-C} observed for the zinc and mercury complexes point to the bidentate coordination as in the other cases. The far-IR spectra of cobalt(II) and mercury(II) chloro and copper(II) nitrate and zinc(II) bromo complexes show absorption bands at 321, 304, 276, 375, 300, 280, 431, 376, 438, 393, 276, 346, 285 and 228 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the Co-O, Co-N, Co-Cl, Fe-O, Fe-N, Fe-Cl, Cu-O, Cu-N, Zn-O, Zn-N, Zn-Br, Hg-O, Hg-N and Hg-Cl stretching frequencies respectively^{12,13}.

Electronic and magnetic moments :

The electronic spectrum of copper(II) complex shows a broad band in the range 11400–13000 cm⁻¹ which suggests a distorted octahedral geometry for this complex. The complex is green in colour and the μ_{eff} value is 1.89 B.M., which is indicative of the absence of metal-metal interaction. Iron(III) complex registers highly intense CT

band at 21.739 cm⁻¹. The low intensity d-d absorption in this complex is masked by a relatively intense CT band. The μ_{eff} value of 5.7 B.M. points to a high-spin octahedral structure for the complex. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the Co^{II} complex exhibits intense bands at 5449, 8980 and 15540 cm⁻¹ which are assignable to the ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₂, ⁴T₂ → ⁴T_{1g} (F) and ⁴A₂ → ⁴T_{1g} (P) respectively. The above observation suggests a four coordinate environment around Co^{II}¹⁴. From the electronic spectral data, the frequencies ν₁, ν₂, ν₃, β, β% and LFSE are found to be 5449, 8980, 15540, 56 and 44 respectively. The ν₃/ν₂ ratio is determined using the Tanabe-Sugano diagram to derive information regarding ν₁. The percentage ionic character is 56, which indicates its high-spin nature and the ground state as ⁴A₂ which has no inherent orbital angular momentum¹¹.

The EPR spectrum :

The EPR spectrum of copper(II) nitrate complex recorded at LNT (77 K) shows that the g_{||} is less than 2.3 which indicates a covalent environment¹⁵ and the spectrum is anisotropic. The complex is tetragonally elongated with g_{||} > g_⊥ and the unpaired electron is in the d_{x²-y²} orbital. The axial symmetry parameter G value is greater than four which suggests that the exchange interaction between the metal centers is negligible¹⁶. The g_{||} and α² values are 2.29 and 0.98 respectively which suggests that the bond is sufficiently covalent and that the unpaired electron spends 3% of its time on the ligand donor atom.

NMR spectra of d¹⁰ complexes :

¹H NMR spectra of the d¹⁰ complexes are recorded in DMSO-d₆. The multiplet at δ 7.26–7.44 ppm in the free ligand remains practically unaltered in the complexes and appears at δ 7.30–7.50 ppm. The -N(CH₂)₂ protons of piperidine ring experience a slight downfield shift by about δ 0.08–0.18 ppm which supports the coordination of amino nitrogen atom to zinc. The -CH₂-N< protons of piperidine ring undergo a slight downfield shift to δ 0.03 ppm which is probably due to the shielding zone created by the metal environment. Similarly, (CH₂)₂-CH₂ protons experience a slight downfield shift by about δ 0.06–0.19 ppm. Based on the above observation tetrahedral geometry is proposed for the d¹⁰ complexes. Based on the above physical data the tentative structures of PMA and its metal complexes are given in Fig. 1.

Thermal decomposition and evaluation of kinetic parameters :

The TG of PMA shows a double stage decomposition pattern. The decomposition temperature ranges for the

Fig. 1. Structures of PMA and its metal chelates.

first and second stages are 150–250° and 250–450°C. An exotherm at 232°C may be due to oxidative degradation of the ligand. The TG pattern of FeCl₃.PMA.H₂O recorded in nitrogen atmosphere shows a small mass loss in the range 110–120°C which is due to the removal of one molecule of water. This observation is also supported by the evidence in the IR spectrum for the presence of coordinated water. The anhydrous product is stable up to 500°C. The mass of the final residue corresponds to the formation of FeO (cal. 15.4%, obs. 15.0%). The TG

curve of CoCl₂.PMA complex records a two stage decomposition pattern and the temperature ranges are 225–400° and 425–700°C and the mass of the final residue does not correspond to any stoichiometric cobalt compound. ZnBr₂.PMA is stable up to 200°C and the first stage decomposition temperature range is 200–300°C. The second stage decomposition starts at 300°C and ends at 400°C. An exotherm is observed at 375°C which is due to the volatilization of organic moiety. The mass of the residue corresponds to ZnO (cal. 44.1%, obs. 45.0%). On further raising the temperature, it undergoes a gradual mass loss up to 750°C. The mass of the residue corresponds to the formation of ZnO (cal. 15.9%, obs. 16.0%). The thermogram of mercury(II) chloride complex shows a rapid decomposition in the range of 150–400°C and a maximum mass loss is observed at 250°C. The mass of the final residue corresponds to the formation of HgO (cal. 38.9%, obs. 39.0%).

Evaluation of thermodynamic and kinetic parameters :

The kinetic and thermodynamic parameters such as E , A , ΔS^\ddagger , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger have been evaluated using Coats-Redfern¹⁷ and Madhusudanan-Krishanan-Ninan¹⁸ equations and are presented in Table 2. The satisfactory value of $R = 1$ is in agreement with the experimental data. The order parameter was found to be one for all the complexes. The negative value of ΔS^\ddagger shows that the complexes are more ordered in the activated state than the reactants and the reactions are slow as indicated by a gradual mass change in the thermogram at the corresponding temperature.

Biological studies :

The data on the percentage of bacterial growth are presented in Table 3. The inhibition in the growth of gram positive organism produced by various concentra-

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters for PMA and its iron(III), cobalt(II), zinc(II) and mercury(II) complexes

Compd.	Stage	CR				MKN			
		E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH kJ ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG kJ ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH kJ ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG kJ ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
PMA	I	86.80	44.63	78.45	100.98	87.06	44.36	78.67	101.07
	II	123.15	17.28	113.40	123.53	123.42	17.33	113.66	123.83
FeCl ₃ .PMA.H ₂ O	I	57.56	143.77	46.12	145.03	57.93	142.99	46.49	144.86
CoCl ₂ .PMA	I	81.73	94.29	70.95	135.05	82.02	93.83	71.25	132.05
	II	44.74	183.67	30.22	190.56	45.23	182.54	30.71	190.77
ZnBr ₂ .PMA	I	64.61	100.76	55.48	110.80	64.88	100.21	55.75	110.77
	II	192.69	281.14	181.91	129.33	192.91	81.08	182.13	129.60
	III	130.50	84.61	115.65	191.21	130.93	84.21	116.08	191.28
HgCl ₂ .PMA		33.66	166.84	24.96	112.22	33.97	165.81	25.27	112.00

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of PMA and its iron(III), cobalt(II) and zinc(II) complexes against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*

Compd.	<i>E. coli</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>	
	Concentration	Concentration	Concentration	Concentration
	$\mu\text{g/mL}$ (% Inhibition)	$\mu\text{g/mL}$ (% Inhibition)	$\mu\text{g/mL}$ (% Inhibition)	$\mu\text{g/mL}$ (% Inhibition)
	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h
PMA	50 (79)	50 (79)	50 (79)	50 (79)
	100 (96)	100 (96)	100 (96)	100 (96)
	150 (94)	150 (94)	150 (94)	150 (94)
	200 (93)	200 (93)	200 (93)	200 (93)
	250 (90)	250 (90)	250 (90)	250 (90)
$\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot \text{PMA} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	50 (68)	50 (82)	50 (68)	50 (82)
	100 (72)	100 (89)	100 (72)	100 (89)
	150 (70)	150 (90)	150 (70)	150 (90)
	200 (76)	200 (89)	200 (76)	200 (89)
	250 (66)	250 (87)	250 (66)	250 (87)
$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{PMA}$	50 (74)	50 (89)	50 (74)	50 (89)
	100 (75)	100 (94)	100 (75)	100 (94)
	150 (84)	150 (95)	150 (84)	150 (95)
	200 (85)	200 (97)	200 (85)	200 (97)
	250 (85)	250 (91)	250 (85)	250 (91)
$\text{ZnBr}_2 \cdot \text{PMA}$	50 (72)	50 (72)	50 (72)	50 (72)
	100 (73)	100 (92)	100 (73)	100 (92)
	150 (82)	150 (94)	150 (82)	150 (94)
	200 (79)	200 (98)	200 (79)	200 (98)
	250 (79)	250 (95)	250 (79)	250 (95)
Streptomycin	50 (69)	50 (92)	50 (69)	50 (92)
	100 (79)	100 (92)	100 (79)	100 (92)
	150 (83)	150 (95)	150 (83)	150 (95)
	200 (82)	200 (93)	200 (82)	200 (93)
	250 (73)	250 (76)	250 (73)	250 (76)

PMA = 4-Piperidinomethyl antipyrine.

tions of the test compound is compared under identical condition with the inhibition of the growth of the same by penicillin. Similarly, the inhibition of the growth of the gram negative organisms produced by the test compound is compared with those for different concentrations of streptomycin. In all the compounds tested for antimicrobial assay, it is found that activity increases with the increase in the concentration of the test compound. Among the various complexes Zn^{II} bromo complex shows the highest activity and Fe^{III} , chloro complex shows the least activity against the two microorganisms. The Zn^{II} complex is coordinatively unsaturated and hence it exhibits tendency to bind with additional enzymatic -SH groups. In most of the cases, the antimicrobial activity increases upon complexation due to the presence of transition metal

ion. Cobalt(II) complex is also active against both the microorganisms. This may be due to the fact that Co^{II} is an essential micronutrient during transcription and transformation of nucleic acids. When the synthesis of the cell wall is blocked by the complex, the high internal osmotic pressure leads to the extrusion of bacterial protoplasm through defects in the supporting structures and this in turn leads to lysis of the cell. It is found that coordinatively unsaturated complexes are more active than the saturated complexes. Order of activity against *Escherichia coli* is : Zn^{II} bromo complex > Co^{II} chloro complex > PMA > Fe^{III} bromo complex. Order of activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* is : Co^{II} chloro complex > Zn^{II} bromo complex > PMA > Fe^{III} bromo complex (monohydrate).

Order of thermal stability of PMA complex is

$\text{ZnBr}_2 \cdot \text{PMA} > \text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{PMA} > \text{PMA} > \text{FeCl}_3 \cdot \text{PMA} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$. On correlating the thermal stability of PMA and its metal complexes with the antimicrobial activity, it is seen that higher the thermal stability, higher is the antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

All the reagents used for synthesizing PMA and its metal complexes were of A.R. grade and the solvents used were commercial products of the highest purity and were further purified by standard methods.

Synthesis of PMA and its metal complexes :

The compound 4-piperidinomethyl antipyrine (PMA) is synthesized using Mannich reaction. 18.8 g of (0.1 mol) of antipyrine is stirred with 9 mL of formaldehyde (0.1 mol) and mixed with 10.6 mL of piperidine (0.1 mol) and 1.2 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid at ice cold condition. The reaction mixture is kept at room temperature for about 24 h. After 24 h when the solution becomes clear, it is neutralized using sodium hydroxide solution. The resulting mixture is extracted with CHCl_3 . The CHCl_3 layer is kept for evaporation in a water bath. Pale yellow coloured waxy solid separates out. The crude product is washed with ether and dried in a desiccator (yield 73%). Iron(III) chloride complex is prepared by mixing the solution of PMA in CHCl_3 with $\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in EtOH in 1 : 1 mole ratio and the solution is stirred well. Reddish brown coloured precipitate obtained is washed with ethanol and dried in a vacuum oven. Copper(II) nitrate and cobalt(II) chloride complexes are prepared by heating the solution of PMA with $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively both mixed in acetone in 1 : 1 mole ratio. Green and peacock blue coloured products obtained respectively are filtered, washed with acetone and dried in a vacuum oven. Zinc(II) bromo and mercury(II) chloro complexes are prepared by treating the corresponding metal salt solution with EtOH with PMA in 2-proH in 1 : 1 mole ratio. Pale yellow product which separated out immediately is filtered, washed with EtOH and dried in a vacuum oven.

The elemental analysis (C, H and N) were carried out using LECO-CHN 600 elemental analyser. The conductance data were obtained in $10^{-3} M$ DMF solution at room temperature using a Systronics Direct Reading Digital Conductivity Bridge-304 with a dip type conductivity cell. Infrared spectral measurements were made for the free ligand and its metal complexes as KBr pellets using Perkin-Elmer 1430 Ratio Recording Spectrophotometer. Far infrared ($500\text{--}50\text{ cm}^{-1}$) measurements were made for

the ligand and a few of its metal complexes to determine M-N, M-O and M-X frequencies and the measurements were made using Broker IFS 66 FT-IR spectrometer. The electronic spectra of the complexes in the UV-visible region were measured using JASCO UVIDECE 430 B double beam spectrophotometer using DMF as the solvent. The diffuse reflectance spectral measurements (200–800 nm) were made on Carry 2390 Spectrophotometer in MgCO_3 medium. The magnetic measurements of the complexes at room temperature were made by using Gouy magnetic balance. Proton NMR spectra of the ligand and its d^{10} metal ion complexes were recorded using JEOL GSX 400NB 400MHZ FTNMR spectrometer using TMS as internal reference and $\text{DMSO-}d_6/\text{CDCl}_3$ as solvent at ambient temperature. A Varian E4-X-Band EPR spectrometer was used for recording the EPR spectra of copper(II) complexes both at RT and LNT at X band frequencies. Polycrystalline DPPH was used as a "g" marker. Simultaneous TG and DTA patterns of some of the metal complexes were recorded on Shimadzu Thermal analyser DT-40 in an atmosphere of air at a linear heating rate of 10°C using heated alumina as the standard reference material.

Antimicrobial screening :

For screening the ligand and its metal complexes for antimicrobial activities, Serial Tube Dilution Technique was followed in which the turbidities of the bacterial suspensions were measured using a Systronics Nephelo-Turbidity meter-131¹⁰. The percentage of bacterial growth inhibition produced by a particular concentration of the test compound was calculated from the measure of the control and the turbidity of the particular test compound. The relation used is % inhibition = $[(T_c - T_o) / T_c] \times 100$, where, T_c = turbidity of the control and T_o = turbidity of the specific compound or the test compound.

Conclusion :

This work deals with the synthesis and characterization of PMA and its metal chelates with iron(III), cobalt(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and mercury(II). The bidentate mode of chelation of PMA is confirmed by IR and ^1H NMR spectral studies. The geometry of the complexes are assigned by UV and EPR spectral studies. The thermal and kinetic studies indicate the order parameter for all the complexes as one. On correlating the thermal stability of the complexes with the antimicrobial activity, it is concluded that higher the thermal stability, higher is the antimicrobial activity.

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